

TEACHERS' EMPOWERMENT AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF ENGLISH TEACHERS AMONG PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF SARANGANI PROVINCE: BASIS FOR ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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Abstract: This study aimed to determine the significant influence of teachers' empowerment on the teaching performance of public secondary English school teachers in the Division of Sarangani, Philippines. A quantitative descriptive correlational method of research was employed using adapted survey questionnaires. The respondents of the study were 161 English teachers in public secondary schools. Using weighted mean, results revealed that the level of teachers' empowerment is highly empowered, while their teaching performance is described as very satisfactory. Using Pearson r, data revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between the teachers' empowerment and the teaching performance of English teachers. Linear regression analysis showed that teachers' empowerment significantly influences the teaching performance of English teachers. Trust as a domain of teachers' empowerment was the best predictor of the teaching performance of English teachers based on the highest beta standardized coefficient value. The proposed enhancement program may be utilized to improve teachers' empowerment and teaching performance of English teachers.

Keywords: Educational management, English teachers, teachers' empowerment, teaching performance, enhancement program, quantitative descriptive correlational, public secondary school, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Public school teachers are loaded with work in the educational arena, including non-teaching responsibilities that significantly affect their teaching effectiveness. Teachers need to be more empowered during this significant academic transition. When implementing the new teaching and learning functions, they tend to focus more on following orders from the Department of Education (DepEd). In effect, teachers barely participated in the decision-making of the school (Özgenel & Mert, 2019)

Many teachers, especially those who teach English, don't do well in the classroom because they feel they need to be more motivated and in charge. Also, case studies showed that mental and personal disorders like emotional distress, burnout, and health problems could affect teachers' performance. The adverse effects of these trends include declining job satisfaction, reduced ability to meet students' needs, and a declining sense of empowerment among teachers (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Harmsen et al., 2019; Kelley et al., 2020)

In DepEd, yearly teacher performance evaluations are facilitated to ensure regular performance monitoring. The validation was based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) that the teacher filled out. This uniform instrument gives the organization a place to agree on standards of behavior and performance that help people grow professionally and personally. With this in mind, evaluating whether teachers teach 21st-century skills under the standard performance rating outlined in the Department of Education's reform initiative is pertinent (Burgos & Meer, 2021; Lagrisola, 2019; Llego, 2017).

Furthermore, teachers have traditionally been given complete autonomy regarding school improvement initiatives. However, during the pandemic outbreak, most of these initiatives have caused some teachers to feel disempowered due to the strict Inter-agency Task Force (IATF) protocols and strict compliance of the DepEd orders cascading to the local schools. This lack of freedom and input could make teachers feel like they are less capable of doing their jobs. The study conducted by researchers in the Philippines revealed that the teachers of DepEd Region XII displayed a moderate level of performance-related skills, abilities, initiatives, and productivity, exceeding requirements in many work performance areas (David et al., 2018; Kadtong et al., 2017; Tumusiime, 2022).

Based on the literature, researchers stressed that giving teachers more power to make decisions improves their commitment, knowledge, and student achievement. Some studies have found that when teachers are empowered, their self-esteem goes up, they are happier at work, and they are more productive. Likewise, they get along better with their coworkers and know more about their subjects. In some cases, student achievement goes up. However, no substantial evidence shows a relationship between increased decision-making and teacher effectiveness. Linking teachers' empowerment in professional learning communities and their teaching performance in teaching English is another research aspect that needs to be conducted specifically in public schools (Ahmed & Malik, 2019; Jiang et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2019).

The arguments above have pushed the researcher to examine how teachers in public secondary schools in the Division of Sarangani Province are empowered and how well they do their jobs in the new standard educational setup. Also, based on previous literature, no study was conducted on how much teachers can help their students learn while the educational crisis is still at its worst.

1.1 Research Objective

This study aimed to determine the significant influence of teachers' empowerment on the teaching performance of English teachers among public secondary schools in the division of Sarangani Province, particularly in the municipalities of Maasim, Kiamba, and Maitum (MAKIMA) school districts. Specifically, it sought an answer to the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of teachers' empowerment of English teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 Professional Development,
 - 1.2 Trust,
 - 1.3 Status, and
 - 1.4 Collaboration.
2. To ascertain the level of teaching performance of English teachers;
3. To determine the significant relationship between teachers' empowerment and the teaching performance of English teachers;
4. To determine what domain of teachers' empowerment best influences the teaching performance of English teachers; and
5. To develop an enhancement program based on the findings of the study.

1.2 Theoretical Framework

This study was rooted in Rappaport's Theory of Empowerment (1990), Kanter (1993), Kluska et al. (2004), and the Performance Theory by Goofman (1970) & Zimmerman (2000).

The empowerment theory says empowering people means considering their needs, rights, and choices. It covers a wide range of ways to care about the powerless. The theory of structural empowerment includes a discussion of organizational behavior and empowerment. This theory says empowerment creates workplaces where employees can access information, resources, support, and opportunities to learn and grow. Also, Kluska et al. (2004) supported the idea that empowered employees have a feeling of competence, autonomy, job meaningfulness, and an ability to impact the organization. When

employees are free, they are more loyal to the company, more responsible for their work, and better able to do their jobs well (Kanter, 1993).

In the same way, Zimmerman's (2000) empowerment theory describes empowerment as both a value orientation for working in the community and a theoretical model for understanding the process and results of trying to control and influence decisions that affect one's life, the way an organization works and the quality of life in a community.

Goffman's performance theory from 1970 also says that everyone in our society puts on a show. Everything we do is a performance designed as a signal system for ourselves and others about our place within our social group. Performances seek to reinforce and communicate our identities in society. They tend to believe that the character they see possesses it, that the task he performs will have the consequences that are implicitly claimed for it, and that, in general, matters are what they appear to be." Goffman thought that we use "impression management" to show other people how we want them to see us.

The above theories of empowerment were used to figure out how empowered the teachers were because they took into account things that could change how empowered the teachers were. On the other hand, the theory of performance suits the concepts used in this study because it is rooted in the idea that every performance action has its consequences.

1.3 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework showed the independent and dependent variables of this undertaking. It sought to assess the level of teacher empowerment when it comes to professional development, trust, status, and collaboration, as well as the level of teacher performance and the impact that will lead to the development of an enhancement program.

The literature says that empowerment is a practice that gives teachers a sense of motivation, makes them feel more confident in their knowledge and skills, and gives them the freedom to do what they think is best and most important for a certain reason. Also, teacher quality is essential. It is the most influential school-related factor in student achievement. The essential factor in the teaching-learning process is the teacher. The teacher sets the tone and lighting of the classroom.

So, good teachers are necessary for the education system to work well and improve the quality of learning. Teaching is the most prestigious profession in the world. They are the focal point of the educational system and the nation's driving force. They add characteristics, strategies, and styles to their perceptual and cognitive interactions with the world (Cheung, 2020; Kadtong et al., 2017; Keiler, 2018; Looney et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. METHOD

This study quantified data using a quantitative approach and typically applied specific statistical analysis. The descriptive-correlational research design is the first technique used in this study. A scientific approach entails watching and describing a subject's activity without altering it. (Novitasari, Hutagalung, Amri, Nadeak, & Asbari, 2021; Siedlecki, 2020). This method describes how much power Maasim, Kiamba, and Maitum District teachers have and how well they do their jobs.

The study's respondents were the 161 English teachers who regularly taught in public secondary schools, specifically in Maitum, Kiamba, and Maasim in the division of Sarangani. This study used the complete enumeration strategy, where all population members are respondents. The total teaching force of the identified schools was considered the study's subject.

Further, the data were collected in the form of a survey. After the survey, the teacher respondents were likewise asked about their rating on their Individual Performance & Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) based on the previous year. After getting all of the instruments back, the researcher made the dummy tables that would be used to combine the data. These data were then treated with appropriate statistical tools. After this, the gathered data will be into meaningful information through a data analysis wherein the data will be easily “converted” into useful information as a basis for decision-making (Kent, 2020; Perera, Nayak & Nguyen, 2022; Taherdoost, 2022).

Moreover, this study treated the objective research numbers 1 and 2 with a weighted mean. It was used to get the average of the values with different weights, specifically, like the case of the Likert scale, where each scale is assigned a weight. scores, the answers from the participants were then interpreted verbally.

For objective number 3, a *Pearson r* was utilized. It tests the degree of relationship between the teachers’ empowerment and the teaching performance of English teachers (Schober, 2018). In addition, a Regression Analysis was used to treat research objective number 4. No statistical tool was employed for research objective number 5.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Level of Teacher Empowerment of English Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in the Division of Sarangani

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Professional Development	0.24	4.03	Empowered
Trust	0.22	4.52	Highly Empowered
Status	0.30	4.63	Highly Empowered
Collaboration	0.63	4.30	Highly Empowered
Overall	0.33	4.37	Highly Empowered

Table 1 presents the overall teacher empowerment from the lens of the English teachers in the municipalities of Maasim, Kiamba, and Maitum, measured in terms of professional development, trust, status, and collaboration.

Generally, the level of teacher empowerment of English teachers got an overall mean of 4.37, verbally described as *highly empowered*. It means that the teachers were inspired and supported. To give a good education, you must be willing to take risks, work on your professional development, and work with your peers.

The survey results showed that the professional development indicator got a mean score of 4.03, verbally described as "empowered" when spoken. Under the teacher empowerment domain, on the other hand, trust got a mean score of 4.52 and was verbally described as "highly empowered." Status got a score of 4.63, and collaboration got a score of 4.30. Moreover, the top 3 domains with the highest scores are status, trust, and collaboration. At the same time, professional development is the domain with the lowest score. The overall scores indicate a high level of teacher empowerment, even though there were some things to consider for the indicators needing improvement.

Table 2: Level of Teaching Performance of English Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in the Division of Sarangani

	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Teaching Performance of English Teachers	0.25	4.25	Very Satisfactory

Table 2 presents the level of teaching performance of English teachers among public secondary schools in the municipalities of Maasim, Kiamba, and Maitum. It talks about what the respondents did, how they did it, what they thought about it, and how they acted in their teaching environment. It shows up on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) that public school teachers in the Department of Education use. It helps them reach their educational and professional goals while doing their job. This tool is a standard form that teachers use to link their accomplishments, needs for professional development, and contributions to the department's vision and mission. It can be gleaned from the table

that English teachers had an overall mean teacher performance of 4.25. The result is described as *very satisfactory*. The result is that the teachers manifest high-quality teaching about the day-to-day interactions in the classroom and the different pedagogical approaches used to engage, motivate, and challenge learners.

Table 3: Relationship between Teachers’ Empowerment and Teaching Performance of English Teachers among Public Secondary Schools

Independent Variable (Teachers’ Empowerment)	Dependent Variable	R	P-value	Remarks
Professional Development	Teaching Performance	0.241*	0.002	Significant
Trust	Teaching Performance	0.244**	0.002	Significant
Status	Teaching Performance	0.190**	0.016	Significant
Cooperation	Teaching Performance	0.134	0.091	Not Significant
Overall (Teachers’ Empowerment)	Overall (Teaching Performance)	0.191*	0.015	Significant

*significant at 0.05

**significant at 0.01

Table 3 presents the relationship between the level of teacher empowerment among English teachers and their performance based on their IPCRF. The overall mean of the independent variable is 4.37, *“highly empowered.”* The dependent variable yielded a mean of 4.25, described as *Very Satisfactory*.

In addition, using the Pearson r Product Correlation Coefficient, the results yielded an $r=0.191$ and $p=0.015$. Since $p<0.05$, there is a significant relationship between teacher empowerment and teachers' performance among English teachers.

Therefore, it means that their performance will also boost when teachers are empowered. Results show how important it is to encourage and uplift teachers so that they can perform well; it is also crucial to support teachers and foster environments where they can flourish because teachers are essential in educating students and influencing their lives. In this case, the H0 or null hypothesis is rejected upon testing the research hypothesis because variables have a significant relationship.

The empowerment of the teachers by their school heads plays a crucial role in their very satisfactory workplace performance. There is a higher level of performance when school heads engage their teachers in making decisions and offer opportunities to develop. Therefore, teachers should be empowered, and their school heads should give them the autonomy to create anything to improve their capacity. Also, they are one of the main conditions that must be paid attention to in education development to contribute to improving human resource quality because high-quality education will develop if the teachers can escalate their capacity systematically and sustainably (Anđić & Vorkapić, 2017; Brandt et al., 2019; Hiller & Reichhart, 2017).

Table 4: Significance of the Influence of Teachers’ Empowerment on Teaching Performance of English Teachers among Public Secondary Schools

Individual Predictors	Beta Coefficients	T	p-value	Remarks
Professional Development	0.241	3.128	0.002	Significant
Trust	0.244	3.167	0.002	Significant
Status	0.190	2.441	0.016	Significant
Collaboration	0.134	1.702	0.091	Not Significant
Holistic Model				
Predictors Combined	R ²	F	p-value	Remarks
	0.145	6.594	0.000	Significant

* p < 0.05

Table 4 presents the domain of teachers' empowerment that best influences the teaching performance of English teachers in the municipalities of Maasim, Kiamba, and Maitum. The results in the table display the regression coefficients to test the significant influence of overall teacher empowerment on the teaching performance of English teachers.

Through regression analysis, the results showed that there is a strong link between teachers' empowerment and how well English teachers teach. The original hypothesis was not accepted since the results showed an F value of 6.594 and a *p-value* of 0.05. It further indicates that all domains of teachers' empowerment, when combined, are significant predictors of the teaching performance of English teachers. Hence, it signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Moreover, the R2 value of 0.145 implies that teachers' empowerment influenced 14.50 percent of the variance of the teaching performance of English teachers, while other factors contributed to the remaining 85.50 percent. Thus, the percentage of the variance in the teaching performance of English teachers accounts for only a tiny part of the influence of teachers' empowerment. Specifically, the data revealed that among the domains of teachers' empowerment, only *professional development* (T=3.128; p<0.05), *trust* (T=3.167; p < 0.05), and *status* (T=2.441; p< 0.05) are significant predictors of the teaching performance of English teachers. Hence, the singular capacities of each of these domains can significantly influence the teaching performance of English teachers.

Also, based on the highest beta standardized coefficient value, the trust domain is the best predictor of how well English teachers teach compared to the other domains of teachers' empowerment, which are significant predictors. The standardized beta coefficient of 0.244 signifies that every one-unit increase in teachers' empowerment could lead to a 24.40 percent improvement in the teaching performance of English teachers.

This result was the same as what Holmes and Parker (2018) found: that trust between teachers was a strong predictor of teacher empowerment. It highlights the positive role of teachers' trust in colleagues for their participation in decision-making, their perceptions of professional growth, and their impact on colleagues. It provides empirical evidence that trust relationship among teachers facilitates teacher empowerment.

Trust is evident in every organization when teachers are highly valued and respected. The teacher's deep educational knowledge, actions, and values, and how they engage respectfully with others with empathy and humility, are manifestations of deep trust. A good relationship with colleagues will likely grow when teachers have good emotional intelligence and self-awareness. Specifically, teachers' trust in the principal and colleagues makes it more likely that they will trust their students (van der Werff et al., 2019).

ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM MATRIX FOR TEACHERS’ EMPOWERMENT AND TEACHER PERFORMANCE

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Activities	Budgetary Requirement	Persons Involved	Time Frame	Success Indicators
I- TEACHER EMPOWERMENT A. Professional Development	To provide more training for teachers on handling students at risk and special training for new students or transferees. To Provide a supplemental training workshop for teachers on the	Keep the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) going once a month and combine local training on how to deal with students at risk with special training for new students or those who have moved schools. Conduct a continuous webinar or face-to-face seminar on the most recent teaching	School MOOE	School Admin, Teachers, Human Resource Officer	August 2022- June 2023 August 2022-	Activity attendance sheets *MOVs like the picture Activity Designs Approved Training Matrix Activity attendance sheets

	recent teaching pedagogy or methods To Provide scientific training for teachers that are applicable in today's set-up	methods or strategies, including the scientific training required by teachers in today's educational environment.	School MOOE	School Admin, Teachers, Human Resource Officer	June 2023	*MOV's like the picture Activity Designs Approved Training Matrix
B. Trust	To provide regular teacher team-building activities to further enhance the teachers' trust in their administrator.	Conduct regular team-building activities emphasizing the value of trust, delegation, and empowerment.	Local Funds (MOOE)	School Admin, Teachers, Human Resource Officer	Once every quarter	Activity attendance sheets Activity design Approved activity matrix
C. Status	To strengthen teachers' social and mental health by regularly recognizing every accomplishment they make.	Maintain a regular seminar on social-mental health for teachers. Regularly conduct positive reinforcement programs that let teachers know when they have done something great within the month.	Local Funds (MOOE),PTA	School Admin, Teachers, parents, Human Resource Officer	August 2022-June 2023	Program attendance sheets Activity design Approved program matrix
D. Collaboration	To Provide broader room or chances for teachers to collaborate with their co-teachers, Establish autonomy for the teachers to make decisions and exercise their profession freely.	Provide a school-based designation order for teachers stating their scope of work. During SLAC sessions, teachers are encouraged to strengthen collaborations with their peers.	Local Funds (MOOE), Gender and Development (GAD) funds	School Admin, Teachers, HR officer	August 2022-June 2023	Activity attendance sheets *other MOV's like pictures *Designation orders *SLAC activity matrix
II-TEACHER PERFORMANCE	To maintain the level of teachers' performance at "Very Satisfactory"	Regular conduct of teacher training and recognition.	School MOOE	School Admin, Teachers	All-year-round	IPCRF, certificates, plaques, Attendances, activities

Proposed Intervention Program

The table shows the enhancement program matrix for teachers' empowerment and teacher performance. The matrix shows the areas of concern, goals, activities, budgetary needs, people involved, time frame, and success indicators. Additionally, the contents of the proposed intervention activity design are the following: identifying information, rationale, objectives, expected participants, budgetary requirements (proposed), working committees per municipality/district, and an indicative schedule of activities.

4. DISCUSSION

Level of Teachers' Empowerment of English Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in the Division of Sarangani Province

The high level of teacher empowerment among English teachers is due to the high indicator level, as revealed in the study's findings. Among the four domains, prestige is the highest. The *status* domain connotes a high level of teacher empowerment. It means that the teaching profession provided them with a feeling of high social status. Because of the support from their respective school principals, they have demonstrated dedication to their colleagues, stakeholders, and the Department of Education organization. Also, because their peers respect and admire them, they feel they must give back to their community.

The results of this study align with the studies of several authors (Mardapi & Herawan (2019); Salimi & Abdi (2018); Ghorbani et al. (2018). Their research showed that teachers' status predicts their emotional, organizational commitment, continued organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, commitment to being a professional teacher, and professional commitment to teaching work. Furthermore, teachers with a high sense of status in their work and organization are more likely to feel committed to their organization.

The second highest indicator is *trust*. The results of the study revealed that domain *trust* is highly empowered. It is where the school administrator treats everyone fairly according to DepEd or school policies. It demonstrates that the teachers are comfortable being themselves in whatever endeavor they wish to pursue about their tasks as teachers of their students and, ultimately, in providing quality education.

The school heads trust the English teachers to carry out their tasks with minimal supervision. They work at their own pace, free of stress and external pressure to complete their tasks. The result of the study by Balyer et al. (2017) supports these findings. It says that one of an administrator's jobs is to give teachers the freedom to handle problems in the classroom and plan school activities on their own. This includes building good communication and relationships with them to build trust. It is because once the principals and teachers trust and support each other, the working relationships within the school organization produce positive outcomes.

In addition, the other domains, such as professional development, significantly contributed to the high level of teachers' empowerment. Teacher empowerment involves investing in teachers and giving them the right to participate in any training for professional development. Being an empowered teacher means having enough skills, resources, and freedom to give every student the education they deserve. So empowerment is also shown by how it helps teachers become more motivated, improves students' problem-solving skills, and teaches students how to become empowered. All of these things are important for improving how well every student learns. In the context of school leadership, teachers being empowered is also seen as a chance to make decisions together, improve their professional status, make schools more appealing to students, build relationships based on trust, and improve how teachers talk to each other (Brandt et al., 2019).

Unquestionably, teacher empowerment is one of the most important parts of teachers' long-term professional development, which helps them become the best teachers they can be for their students. Education is intrinsically related to human development and is crucial in managing poverty alleviation, health promotion, sustainable livelihoods, and a sustainable environment. Education should sustain and realize human potential. So, a country will be great and keep growing if it can improve the quality of education in a way that lasts (Mardapi & Herawan, 2019; Ghorbani, Jafari, & Sharifian, 2018).

The demands for quality education will go unmet if teachers do not have the opportunity to empower themselves. Empowerment can also be considered a way for a company's leader to show appreciation for his or her employees (Mardapi & Herawan, 2019; Nordgren, Kristiansson, Liljekvist, & Bergh, 2020).

Moreover, the high level of teacher empowerment in terms of professional development implies that the respondents grew professionally under the direction of their respective school heads. The school has provided activities to help them learn more about their craft. The teachers' self-esteem needs should be satisfied, especially their incredibly professional development-related ones. According to Balyer, Ozcan, & Yildiz (2017), the world and teaching approaches are changing. To react to these changes, teachers should seek professional development. Their efforts to get a master's degree and on-the-job training may help them see things more clearly, which could improve how they teach. Therefore, their administrators should support their developmental efforts. Teachers' empowerment is an essential aspect of developing their professional competence.

Higher education institutions in the Philippines ensure that their teachers grow in the profession through professional development activities. With this rule, schools must give all their teachers the same chance to grow as professionals. The school administrator may send their teachers to seminars and workshops locally and abroad. They may also be allowed to present their research in international research forums. Professional growth is essential to teacher empowerment (Mukeredzi, 2022; Kramarski & Michalsky, 2017), especially when it comes to giving students a good education and teaching (Mukeredzi, 2022; Kramarski & Michalsky, 2017).

Hence, professional development is critical to personal and social transformation and improvement (Dehghan, 2020). Tindowen (2019) concluded that teachers have much power because they can grow professionally. Teachers with a very high level of professional growth continue to grow professionally and expand their competencies and skills in their work in their institution (Darling-Hammond & McLaughlin, 2017)

Similarly, teachers are highly empowered in collaboration, as evaluated by the English teachers stationed in the municipalities of Maasim, Kiamba, and Maitum. Most of the respondents work in places where they can work with other teachers. Teachers have an excellent workplace where they can work together to help the Department of Education and the Filipino people reach their goals by giving students a good education. Collaboration and helping teachers do their jobs as teachers are essential parts of building relationships between teachers so that they feel like they are part of a professional community and get personal satisfaction from their work. Teachers have always worked independently, but people who support teacher collaboration think that when teachers work together, they can help each other and the school.

School leaders' efforts to redesign organizational structures through transformations in personnel and job allocations, rescheduling, designing time and space, regular procedures, operations, and integrating technology into the administration system can hinder or drive individual performance to accomplish organizational goals. Successful school leaders navigate organizational changes to establish positive systems so teachers can constantly improve their performance and expand their learning experiences. Simultaneously, school leaders work to enhance school performance by building a collaborative process in which the school staff can be involved in decision-making. Involvement empowers school staff and drives them to believe in their ability to change and reconstruct organizational contexts to meet their needs and goals (Huggins, Klar, Hammonds, & Buskey, 2017).

Lastly, gaining *trust* is one indicator contributing to teacher empowerment. Concerning the social attractiveness of the school, providing trustworthiness and communication, most teachers report that school principals try to make schools more attractive places. They build relationships based on trust and create good communication among teachers by solving problems, organizing social activities, promoting themselves, and being easily accessible. Young administrators, in particular, try to meet teachers' demands, build good relationships with teachers, and organize meetings outside the school. They also believe that administrators cannot do it alone because their roles are limited, and it must be a government policy (Balyer, Ozcan & Yildiz, 2017; Holmes & Parker, 2018)

Once the principals and teachers trust each other, they quickly try new implementations. In addition, the feeling of trust fosters an exchange of information between the principals and teachers and allows them to learn new things from each other. They also talk honestly about the implementations that work or do not work, which means they disclose their deficiencies and make themselves vulnerable. School stakeholders must have trust to communicate sincerely (Kars & Inandi, 2018).

Employees who develop trust in their school administrators are more likely to feel secure and optimistic. An employee that does not trust his/her managers is more likely to think that their job will fail to meet their personal goals, which will, in turn, affect their overall job attitude and job satisfaction negatively (Akar, 2018; Buyukgoze & Ozdemir, 2018; Atik & Celik, 2020).

Level of Teaching Performance of English Teachers among Public Secondary Schools

The respondents have very satisfactory performance as indicated in their respective IPCRF. The teachers demonstrated high-quality teaching about classroom interactions and the various pedagogical approaches used to engage, motivate, and challenge students. In addition, their principal shows support by mentoring and coaching colleagues and leading professional learning workshops.

Teacher quality is essential. It is the most influential school-related factor in student achievement. The most critical factor in the teaching-learning process is the teacher. The teacher sets the tone and lighting of the classroom. So, good teachers are necessary for the education system to work well and improve the quality of learning. Teaching is the most prestigious

profession in the world. Hence, the teacher is the focal point of the educational system. Likewise, they are a nation's driving force. They are the maestros in charge of steering the entire orchestra toward quality education. They also add traits, strategies, and styles to how they see and think about the world (Burgos & Meer, 2021; Cheung, 2020; Kad Tong et al., 2017).

Significant Relationship Between Teachers' Empowerment and Teaching Performance among the English Teachers in Public Secondary Schools

There is a strong link between teachers' power and how well they do their jobs. Furthermore, the teachers' school heads are likely to give them much freedom, which is why they do an excellent job. When school leaders involve their teachers in making decisions and give them chances to grow, teachers do a better job. At the micro level, teacher empowerment enables teachers to apply professional judgment to the daily curriculum and subjects. On a higher level, it is the administration's investment in teachers by giving them the chance and freedom to set the goals and policies of the school.

Significance of the Influence of Teachers' Empowerment on Teaching Performance of English Teachers among Public Secondary Schools

Among the four domains of teacher empowerment, the *trust* domain is the best predictor of the teaching performance of English teachers based on the highest beta standardized coefficient value. It will encourage the employees' continued positive behavior, which may increase job satisfaction. Therefore, teachers who believe their school is committed to them and act voluntarily on their behalf will feel a high level of empowerment and consequently strive to improve their work performance (Bogler & Nir, 2017). Trustworthiness and trust are positive expectations of a person's actions. In this manner, most teachers report that school principals have made efforts to make schools more attractive places, build relationships dependent on trust and create good communication among teachers (Balyer, Ozcan & Yildiz, 2017).

The principals trusted the English teachers to complete their tasks with minimal supervision. They complete their tasks independently, without stress or external pressures. Also, their school principals believed they could handle problems because they knew someone was ready to take over and ensure everything was okay if they failed. They can also concentrate on their work because the working environment is safe.

Studies have shown that trustworthiness is the number one attribute of an admired leader. Through their behaviors, honest leaders ensure and maintain the trust of their followers. Therefore, leaders' behaviors are essential in determining whether their followers develop positive or negative emotions toward them. Studies conducted on leadership styles in schools have revealed that authentic leadership style school principal's leadership style and ethical leadership are associated with teachers' trust level (Kars & Inandi, 2018; Huseyin, 2018).

5. CONCLUSION

The teachers in the division of Sarangani, specifically in the municipalities of Maasim, Kiamba, and Maitum, are described as *highly empowered*. In particular, the professional development domain is one where teachers have the least power. Based on their IPCRF, the level of their teaching performance is "*very satisfactory*." Using the Pearson r correlation coefficient, there is a positive relationship between teacher empowerment and teacher performance. It further implies that when teachers are empowered, their work performance also increases. Furthermore, as a sub-variable of teacher empowerment, trust best influences teachers' performance. Therefore, teachers will perform their best when their superiors and peers trust them.

The overall result of the study conforms with Kanter's theory of structural empowerment, which confirms that when employees are supported, given enough opportunities, and empowered to access the organization's resources, information, and training for professional growth in the workplace, empowerment will likely be promoted (Portes et al., 2018)

Similarly, the result of the study is congruent with the performance theory by Goffman (1970), which affirmed that when an individual is impressed by society, he tends to perform more. In return, empowered employees uphold feelings of competence, autonomy, job meaningfulness, and an ability to impact the organization. In the same case, when the teacher is empowered and trusted, his ability to excel and perform at his best is evident in the academic institution.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the recommendations are as follows:

Teachers' empowerment can be strengthened by emphasizing professional development, specifically in training on handling students at risk, special training in handling new students/transferees, and seminars on the latest teaching methods. Additionally, to improve trust in the school, regular teachers' team-building activities may be undertaken to enhance their

trust in their school administrator. To improve teachers' performance, school administrators may improve their status. Teachers should be trusted and provided with avenues for collaboration via team building, understanding social/mental health in the workplace, and school-based recognition of teachers. The teachers may adopt the enhancement program designed in this research to maintain the level of empowerment and improve the teachers' performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahmed, N., & Malik, B. (2019). Impact of psychological empowerment on job performance of teachers: Mediating role of psychological well-being. *Review of Economics and Development Studies*, 5(3), 451-460.
- [2] Akar, H. (2018). The Relationships between Quality of Work Life, School Alienation, Burnout, Affective Commitment, and Organizational Citizen: A Study on Teachers. *European Journal of Educational Research*, v7 n2 p169-180 2018
- [3] Anđić, D., & Vorkapić, S. T. (2017). Teacher Education for Sustainability: The Awareness and Responsibility for Sustainability Problems. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 19(2), 121-137.
- [4] Atik, S., & Celik, O. T. (2020). An Investigation of the Relationship between School Principals' Empowering Leadership Style and Teachers' Job Satisfaction: The Role of Trust and Psychological Empowerment. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 12(3).
- [5] Balyer, A., Ozcan, K., & Yildiz, A. (2017). Teacher empowerment: School administrators' roles. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 17(70), 1-18.
- [6] Bogler, R., & Nir, A.E. (2017). The importance of teachers' perceived organizational support to job satisfaction: What's empowerment got to do with it? *Journal of Educational Administration*, 50(3), 287-306.
- [7] Brandt, J. O., Bürgener, L., Barth, M., & Redman, A. (2019). Becoming a competent teacher in Education for sustainable development: Learning Outcomes and Processes in teacher education. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*.
- [8] Burgos, E. H., & Meer, T. Q. (2021). Determinants Affecting the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) About Work Satisfaction among Elementary Teachers of IBA District, Division of Zambales, Philippines. *International Journal of Recent Advances in Multidisciplinary Topics*, 2(7), 116-123.
- [9] Buyukgoze and Ozdemir, (2018). The role of occupational concerns on the reality shock expectation. *Studia Psychologica* 58(3): 199-215. DOI:10.2199/sp.2016.03.717.
- [10] Cheung, P. (2020). Teachers as role models for physical activity: Are preschool children more active when their teachers are active? *European Physical Education Review*, 26(1), 101-110.
- [11] Darling-Hammond, L., Burns, D., Campbell, C., Goodwin, A. L., Hammerness, K., Low, E. L., ... & Zeichner, K. (2017). *Empowered educators: How high-performing systems shape teaching quality around the world*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [12] David, C., Ducanes, G., Yee, K. M., & Generalao, I. N. (2018). Teacher education in the Philippines: Are we meeting the demand for quantity and quality? (pp. 18-002). UP CIDS Discussion Paper 18-003. <https://cids.up.edu.ph/publications/discussion-papers/2018-series/18-003>.
- [13] Dehghan, F. (2020). Teachers' perceptions of professionalism: a top-down or a bottom-up decision-making process? Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2020.1725597>
- [14] Ghorbani, S., Jafari, S. E. M., & Sharifian, F. (2018). Learning to Be: Teachers' Competences and Practical Solutions: A Step towards Sustainable Development. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 20(1), 20-45.
- [15] Goofman, E. (1970). *Strategic interaction* (Vol. 1). University of Pennsylvania Press.
- [16] Harmsen, R., Helms-Lorenz, M., Maulana, R., van Veen, K., & van Veldhoven, M. (2019). Measuring general and specific stress causes and stress responses among beginning secondary school teachers in the Netherlands. *International Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 42(1), 91-108.
- [17] Hiller, K., & Reichhart, B. (2017). The motivation of civic education teachers-in-training in the field of education for sustainable development. *Discourse and Communication for Sustainable Education*, 8(1), 81-89.

- [18] Holmes, W. T., & Parker, M. A. (2018). The relationship between behavioral integrity, competence, goodwill, trustworthiness, and motivating language of a principal. *School Leadership & Management*, 38(4), 435-456.
- [19] Huggins, K. S., Klar, H. W., Hammonds, H. L., & Buskey, F. C. (2017). Developing Leadership Capacity in Others: An Examination of High School Principals' Personal Capacities for Fostering Leadership. *International Journal of Education Policy and Leadership*, 12(1), n1.
- [20] Huseyin, A. K. A. R. (2018). Meta-analysis of organizational trust studies conducted in educational organizations between the years 2008-2018. *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, 4(4), 287-302.
- [21] Jiang, Y., Li, P., Wang, J., & Li, H. (2019). Relationships between kindergarten teachers' empowerment, job satisfaction, and organizational climate: a Chinese model. *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 33(2), 257-270.
- [22] Kadtong, M. L., Unos, M., Antok, T. D., & Midzid, M. A. E. (2017). Teaching performance and job satisfaction among teachers at Region XII. *Proceedings Journal of Education, Psychology and Social Science Research*, 4(1).
- [23] Kanter, R.M. (1993). *Men and women of the corporation* (2nd ed.). New York: Basic Books.
- [24] Kars, M., & Inandi, Y. (2018). Relationship between School Principals' Leadership Behaviors and Teachers' Organizational Trust. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 74, 145-164.
- [25] Keiler, L. S. (2018). Teachers' Roles and Identities in student-centered Classrooms. *International journal of STEM education*, 5(1), 1-20.
- [26] Kelley, T. R., Knowles, J. G., Holland, J. D., & Han, J. (2020). Increasing high school teachers' self-efficacy for integrated STEM instruction through a collaborative community of practice. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1), 1-13.
- [27] Kent, R. (2020). *Data construction and data analysis for survey research*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- [28] Kluska, K.M., Laschinger-Spence, H. K., & Kerr, M. S. (2004). Staff nurse empowerment and effort-reward imbalance. *Canadian Journal of Nursing Leadership*, 17(1), 112-128.
- [29] Kramarski, B. (2017). Teachers as agents in promoting students' SRL and performance: Applications for teachers' dual-role training program. In *Handbook of self-regulation of learning and performance* (pp. 223-239). Routledge.
- [30] Lagrisola, V. M. (2019). The Implication of Action Research and Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) on the Performance Rating of Public Elementary and Secondary School Teachers in the Division of Laguna. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2M).
- [31] Llego, M (2017). *Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST)*. Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/philippines-professional-standards-for-teachers/>
- [32] Looney, A., Cumming, J., van Der Kleij, F., & Harris, K. (2018). Reconceptualizing the role of teachers as assessors: teacher assessment identity. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 25(5), 442-467.
- [33] Mardapi, D., & Herawan, T. (2019). Community-based teacher training: Transformation of sustainable teacher empowerment strategy in Indonesia. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 21(1), 48-66.
- [34] Mukeredzi, T. G. (2022). An exploration of workplace learning of center managers and educators in South African Adult Education and Training centers. *Journal of Adult and Continuing Education*, 28(1), 5-26.
- [35] Nordgren, K., Kristiansson, M., Liljekvist, Y., & Bergh, D. (2021). Collegial collaboration when planning and preparing lessons: A large-scale study exploring the conditions and infrastructure for teachers' professional development. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 108, 103513.
- [36] Novitasari, D., Hutagalung, D., Amri, L. H. A., Nadeak, M., & Asbari, M. (2021). Kinerja Inovasi Di Era Revolusi Industri 4.0: Analisis Knowledge-Oriented Leadership Dan Kapabilitas Manajemen Pengetahuan. *Edukatif: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 3(4), 1245-1260
- [37] Özgenel, M., & Mert, P. (2019). The role of teacher performance in school effectiveness. *International journal of educational technology and scientific research*, 4(10), 417-434.

- [38] Perera, C. H., Nayak, R., & Nguyen, L. V. T. (2022). Quantitative Data Presentation and Analysis: Inferential Analysis. In *Social Media Marketing and Customer-Based Brand Equity for Higher Educational Institutions* (pp. 187-215). Springer, Singapore.
- [39] Portes, P. R., González Canché, M., Boada, D., & Whatley, M. E. (2018). Early evaluation findings from the instructional conversation study: Culturally responsive teaching outcomes for diverse learners in elementary school. *American Educational Research Journal*, 55(3), 488-531.
- [40] Rappaport, J. (1990). Research methods and the empowerment social agenda. In P. Tolan, C. Keys, F. Chertok, & L. Jason (Eds.), *Researching Community Psychology* (pp. 51–63). Washington, D.C.: American Psychological Association
- [41] Salimi, J., & Abdi, A. (2018). On the relationship between psychological empowerment and job satisfaction of teachers: Investigating the mediator role of organizational citizenship behavior. *Journal of School Psychology*, 6(4), 70-98.
- [42] Siedlecki, S. L. (2020). Understanding descriptive research designs and methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 34(1), 8-12.
- [43] Taherdoost, H. (2022). Different types of data analysis; data analysis methods and techniques in research projects. *International Journal of Academic Research in Management*, 9(1), 1-9.
- [44] Tindowen, D. J. (2019). Influence of Empowerment on Teachers' Organizational Behaviors. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 8(2), 617-631.
- [45] Tumusiime, P. (2022). *Principals' implementation Of Teacher Performance Appraisal And Development (Tpad) Tool And Teachers'performance In Public Secondary Schools In Kikuyu Constituency* (Doctoral dissertation, Tangaza University College).
- [46] van der Werff, L., Legood, A., Buckley, F., Weibel, A., & de Cremer, D. (2019). Trust motivation: The self-regulatory processes underlying trust decisions. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 9(2-3), 99-123.
- [47] Zhu, J., Yao, J., & Zhang, L. (2019). Linking empowering leadership to innovative behavior in professional learning communities: the role of psychological empowerment and team psychological safety. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 20(4), 657-671.
- [48] Zimmerman, B. J. (2000). Attaining self-regulation. A social cognitive perspective. In *Handbook of self-regulation* (pp. 13-39). Academic Press.